

Foreign Direct Investment as a Key Factor for the Economic Development of Emerging Countries: Evidence from Saudi Arabia

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Abstract

The objective of this paper is to present a study aimed at assessing the relationship between FDI and economic growth in Saudi Arabia. While doing so, the study also looked at the effect that trade openness, real exchange rates, and oil prices have on FDI. We used an Auto-regressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model, which looked at both the short- and long-term effects, in addition to an Error Correlation Model to discern the causal relationship between the two. The results of the Long-term ARDL model indicate that oil prices and the real effective exchange rates do have positive long-term effects on FDI in Saudi Arabia. Additionally, the study found that there was no statistically significant long-term relationship between economic growth and FDI and also between trade openness and FDI. Our study recommends that other factors—such as research and development, corruption, political stability and taxes—be included in future research in this area

Key words: Foreign Direct Investment, Economic Growth, Oil price, Auto-regressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model
JEL Classifications: F21, F41, O16

1 Introduction

Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) is a key component of international transfers in the global economy, as it is crucial in the formation of capital in both developed and developing countries (Iamsiraroj, 2016). Many countries, especially emerging and developing ones, strive to attract FDI because they have an expectation of long-term economic growth stemming from any extra resources resulting from FDI. The attractiveness of FDI is spurred by some intangible factors—such as advanced technology, skills, and even research and development—that aid in the stimulation of economic growth and productivity of the host country (Desbordes, 2017). Additionally, FDI also assists in accessing foreign markets through exports, which also results in economic stability and positive productivity effects.

Saudi Arabia is considered to be one of the largest economies in the Middle East and North Africa (MENA) region. Prior to 1999, the country's FDI inflows were not a crucial part of the government's plan, as the oil sector was predominant, being responsible for over 90% of the national revenue (Alshehry, 2015). The country's investment outflows far exceeded its inflows, which prompted the government to take action to attract FDI and reduce the dependency on oil. Ever since the creation of a General Investment Authority, many policies and measures have been put in place to achieve this objective. This has led the FDI inflows into the country to increase from US\$0.16 billion in 1990 to US\$4.56 billion in 2019, with the GDP growing from around US\$120 billion in 1990 to US\$793 billion in 2019 (World Bank, 2021).

According to Wright (2016), the economic development of Saudi Arabia is now mostly driven by the creation of new industries, with a market liberalization that makes it attractive to private investors in addition to an increased diversification away from oil which has been a major part of its export earnings (Elimam, 2017). According to Elimam (2017), global market competition has been a major factor that has spurred the Saudi Arabian government to boost FDI into the country as it has underscored the importance of capital integration, technological advancement, improved skills and diversification, which all lead to sustainable development.

Private investment in Saudi Arabia has been encouraged widely through various policies geared towards achieving the reforms toward liberalization desired by the government. This is attracting multinational companies that bring FDI into Saudi Arabia, providing various benefits such as entrepreneurial abilities and technological skills, among others, which aid economic integration (Badr and Ayed, 2015). One of the policies—implemented by the government—that encourages private companies to invest in the country is that

investors are allowed to remit their funds abroad through a 15% reduction in their taxes, which, on average, results in an annual saving of around 100,000 riyals (Abdulrahim, 2015).

With the importance of FDI being realized, multiple studies have been conducted in an attempt to define the relationship between FDI and the economic growth of a country. Some studies have shown no relationship between the two, while others have shown that such a relationship does exist. Additionally, it is important to also investigate whether and to what extent economic growth does have an influence on the FDI that a country attracts. The fact that Saudi Arabia is a major oil exporter means that its economic growth is inevitably also linked to the fundamentals that revolve around the oil sector; it is important to take this into account when looking at the effect that FDI has on the economic growth of the country. The objective of our study was to investigate the effect that FDI has on economic growth so as to provide a statistically proven model that will assist in measuring the effect of the primary factors that affect FDI inflows into the country. This was done by means of an Auto-regressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model which looked at both the short- and long-term effects, in addition to an Error Correlation Model used to discern the causal relationship between the two.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Theoretical Literature

The theoretical literature on the effects of FDI on economic growth provides contrasting views. For instance, under the neoclassical models of economic growth—which are considered exogenous—long-term growth can only be the result of technological advancement and/or of the growth of a country's labor force (De Mello, 1997). Models such as that developed by Solow (1957) work under the assumption of diminishing returns of capital inputs, and opine that economies converge to similar steady-state rates of growth under the neoclassical growth theory. This then leads to the conclusion that the effects of FDI on growth are short-term, not having any long-term impacts. However, these exogenous models have been considered to be unrealistic—based on the number of assumptions that they make—and this has led to the development of endogenous models, which are been considered to be more appropriate in relation to looking at the role played by technological change.

Endogenous models of growth—which were developed by Romer (1986) and, later, by Rebelo (1991)—introduce capital in the form of human capital accumulation and research and development. They highlight the externalities that stem from these kinds of capital and argue that FDI boosts the use of new inputs in the production process of the host country. If FDI develops positive externalities and improved productivity, among other benefits, it is then considered to endogenously stimulate the growth of an economy, as it is viewed as a key source of factors that will improve economic growth via FDI inflows (Lucas, 1988). Akinlo (2004) opined that FDI has a positive effect on economic growth only when a country's economy has sufficient absorption capabilities to take in advanced technologies. Furthermore, he argued that, for the benefits of FDI to be fully realized, the host country must have an economy that is characterized by open trade and a relatively stable macroeconomic environment.

However, other studies have noted that FDI has a negative effect on economic growth due to dependency and decapitalization. According to the theory of dependency developed by Amin (1974), FDI inflows do not have an effect on long-term growth, especially in developing countries, as it has the long-term effects of decreasing the growth rate of the economy and the level of inequality. He further argued that FDI can have a decapitalizing effect by diverting capital in the host country into those areas in which FDI is focusing; capital that could have been used in more productive sectors in the country. Bornscheir (1980) further provided examples in developing countries in which the diversion of capital toward industrial sectors detracts from their capital formation capabilities, as much of the capital is concentrated in one sector.

2.2 Empirical Literature

Empirically, Anwar and Cooray (2015) investigated the effect of FDI on economic growth by analyzing panel data for the period between 1970 and 2011 and using a generalized moments methodology. Their findings showed that FDI and remittances had a positive effect on the country's GDP and, in addition, they identified government expenditure, quality of institutions, and human capital as key incentives to FDI inflows into a country. Similarly, Gui-Diby and Renard (2015) used a generalized least squares methodology to look at the relationship between FDI and economic growth in African countries using panel data that spanned the years 1980 to 2009. Their independent variables included industrialization level, market size, international trade, and capital. However, their results showed that industrialization level and market size do not have an impact on the flow of FDI and, as such, on economic growth; but that international trade does have an impact on the latter.

Omri and Kahouli (2014) looked at the relationship between FDI and economic growth in 13 MENA countries for the period 1990 to 2010. They applied a growth model methodology involving the use of simultaneous equations under the generalized method of moments (GMM). Their findings showed a bi-directional causality between economic growth and FDI for each of the 13 countries that were investigated. However, Belloumi (2014), who investigated the relationship between FDI, economic growth, and trade openness in Tunisia over the period 1970-2008, reached conclusions that differed completely from those of Omri and Kahouli (2014). He adopted the ARDL bounds test of cointegration as the methodology for his study, and his findings show that cointegration is present only when FDI is the dependent variable. No Granger causality of FDI on economic growth was found in his study, as opposed to Omri and Kahouli (2014).

Other studies have also looked at the factors that affect the inflows of FDI into countries that have oil as a major export. Such studies explored whether dependency on oil has an effect on the inflow of FDI into a country. For instance, Dal Bianco and Nguyen (2017) looked at Latin American countries during the 1990-2012 period to investigate the effects that oil prices and foreign exchange had had on their FDI inflows. They utilized the generalized autoregressive conditional heteroscedasticity (GARCH) model and found that exchange rate volatility had had a negative impact on FDI, but no relationship between oil price fluctuations and FDI. They further opined that the factors that attract FDI into a country are trade openness and human capital. Conversely, Dias et al. (2014) looked at Brazil, and argued that exchange rate volatility had not had an effect on FDI inflows—unlike the economic shocks of the US, which had.

Temiz and Gokemen (2014) investigated the relationship between FDI and economic growth in Turkey by analyzing quarterly data spanning the 1992-2007 period through the Johansen multivariate cointegration method. They found no such causal relationship, either in the short or the long run. The study conducted by Bayar (2014) on the same country—but with data spanning the 1980-2012 period using the bounds test cointegration method—found cointegration between the variables and a negative relationship between FDI and economic growth both in the short and long run. Conversely, using a time series approach as their methodology, Tahir et al. (2015) found a positive relationship between FDI and economic growth in Pakistan over the 1977-2013 period.

Adopting the ARDL approach, Ridzuan et al. (2017) concluded that FDI had had a positive effect on economic growth in Singapore during the 1970-2013 period, as did Choi and Baek (2017) in their study on India. Iamsiraroj (2016)—who took the ARDL approach in addition to the simultaneous equations model that had been adopted by Omri and Kahouli (2014)—showed that FDI and economic growth were linked by mutual positive effects. Furthermore, his study identified labor, economic freedom, and trade openness to be spurs of economic growth.

3 Research Methodology:

The key methodology adopted for our study was the ARDL method, which was applied in three stages:

1) In the first stage, co-integration was tested in the framework of the Unrestricted Error Correction Model (UECM), Should co-integration of the variables have been found, the second stage would have included the estimation of the long-term equation and then an Error Correction Model (ECM) would have been constructed.

Based on economic theory and on the models applied in previous studies on the same subject, the following equation was estimated for the purpose of measuring the impact of oil price fluctuations on FDI inflows in Saudi Arabia during the 1970-2019 period.

The linear model specification could be presented as:

$$FDI_t = \alpha_1 + \beta_1 GDP_t + \delta_1 EXR_t + \lambda_1 OP_t + \varphi_1 TR_t + \mu_t \quad (1)$$

Where

FDI_t : Net flow of foreign investment Direct (% of GDP)

OP_t: Oil price

EXR_t : Real Effective Exchange rate

GDP_t: GDP per capita (Current SAR).

TR_t : Trade openness

$\alpha, \beta, \delta, \lambda, \varphi$: Parameters of the model μ_t : random error

Pesaran (2001) proposed a bounds test based on the Wald or F-statistics to investigate the presence of long-term relationships. The asymptotic distribution of the F statistics is non-standard under the null hypothesis of no cointegration relationship between the examined variables, irrespective of whether the explanatory variables are purely I(0) or I(1).

The cointegration relationship between oil price and net flow of foreign investment Direct was estimated through ARDL using the bounds test, which is based on the following Unrestricted Error Correction Model (UECM):

$$\Delta FDI_t = b_0 + \sum_{i=1}^p b_1 \Delta FDI_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^p b_2 \Delta EXR_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^p b_3 \Delta GDP_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^p b_4 \Delta OP_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^p b_5 \Delta TR_{t-i} + b_6 OP_{t-1} + b_7 EXR_{t-1} + b_8 GDP_{t-1} + b_9 TR_{t-1} + \mu_t \quad (2)$$

The null hypothesis was tested by considering the unrestricted ECM for domestic investment equation in (2) excluding the variables OP_t, EXR_t, GDP_t and TR_t; more formally, we performed a joint significance test in which the null and alternative hypotheses were:

Ho: $b_6=b_7=b_8=b_9=0$

H1: $b_6 \neq b_7 \neq b_8 \neq b_9 \neq 0$

The long-term ARDL (q1, q2, q3, q4, q5) equilibrium relation was given as:

$$FDI_t = \alpha_0 + \sum_{i=1}^{q_1} \alpha_1 FDI_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^{q_2} \alpha_2 GDP_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^{q_3} \alpha_3 EXR_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^{q_4} \alpha_4 OP_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^{q_5} \alpha_5 TR_{t-i} + \varepsilon_t \quad (3)$$

Where ε_t is defined as the term error and is used more frequently between the FDI_t and its equilibrium level, which is to be filled in the next period. Then, the resulting model is in the form:

The Short-term ARDL equilibrium relation was given as:

$$\Delta FDI_t = c_0 + \sum_{i=1}^q c_1 \Delta FDI_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^q c_2 \Delta GDP_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^q c_3 \Delta EXR_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^q c_4 \Delta OP_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^q c_5 \Delta TR_{t-i} + \eta_t \quad (4)$$

4 Results and Discussion

To assess the nullity of non-cointegration against the alternative hypothesis, we used the annual World Development Indicators (WDI) data for the 1970-2019 period (WDI, 2020). The first procedure in the implementation of any technique of co-integration involves the determination of the degree of integration of each element. For this purpose, we conducted ADF and PP tests.

Table 1 presents the descriptive statistics for our study. The mean value implied that average changes in the variables were small. The skewness result revealed that all variables were positively skewed to the right except FDI, which was found to be negatively skewed to the left. The Jarque-Bera statistics revealed that all the GDP, OP and TR were normally distributed, while FDI and EXR were not normally distributed, as their probability values were found to be lower than 10%, while GDP, OP and TR were 10% and above.

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics Result

	FDI	GDP	OP	TR	EXR
Mean	-1.342946	9.384555	3.551688	4.295531	4.860982
Median	-0.383164	9.241057	3.373762	4.268487	4.783748
Maximum	1.940124	10.13632	4.715545	4.565417	5.510005
Minimum	-7.988945	8.675287	2.542834	4.026929	4.546677
Std. Dev.	2.627934	0.485265	0.658053	0.147897	0.289810
Skewness	-1.022034	0.190069	0.341058	0.213943	1.322405
Kurtosis	3.052962	1.530267	1.853986	1.903375	3.537502
Jarque-Bera	6.968360	3.841032	2.964382	2.309455	12.13988
Probability	0.030679	0.146531	0.227139	0.315143	0.002311
Sum	-53.71784	375.3822	142.0675	171.8212	194.4393
Sum Sq. Dev.	269.3355	9.183803	16.88831	0.853070	3.275597
Observations	40	40	40	40	40

Correlation Matrix Test

Correlation can be a good indicator of multicollinearity, as it shows which variables evolve in the same direction, which in the opposite direction, and which are independent. Table 2 displays the correlation test results; none of the variables were shown to be correlated. OP, EXR and TR were found to have a weak negative correlation with FDI, while GDP was found to have a weak positive one. We therefore concluded that there were no multicollinearity issues among the variables.

Table 2. Correlation Matrix

	FDI	GDP	OP	TR	EXR
FDI	1.0000	0.2415	-0.3231	-0.6338	-0.0459
GDP	0.2409	1.0000	0.9339	0.5194	-0.2805
OP	-0.3228	0.9339	1.0000	0.6190	-0.3998
TR	-0.6332	0.5195	0.6191	1.0000	0.0973
EXR	-0.0459	-0.2805	-0.3998	0.0973	1.0000

Unit Root Test Result

Table 3 displays the results of the unit root test for the degree of integration between the variables of interest. The OP variable was found to be stationary at the level when ADF and PP were employed. The other variables (GDP, EXR and TR) were found to be stationary at first difference. The I(0) and I(1) variables were found to be integrated. Overall, our variables were found to fulfill the stationary condition for the adoption of ARDL in our analysis. For this purpose, the ARDL method was used to incorporate the model. The main advantage of this method lies in the fact that it eliminates the need to assign variables in I(1) or I(0). Moreover, compared to normal co-integration, there is no need for unit root pre-testing (Akinlo 2006).

Table 1: Results of the ADF and PP unit root tests

	ADF test				PP test			
	Levels		First difference		Levels		First difference	
	[t - bar]	p - value	[t - bar]	p - value	[t - bar]	p - value	[t - bar]	p - value
FDI	-4.2174	[0.0032]	-6.1403***	[0.0000]	-4.0724	[0.2437]	-4.2187**	[0.0232]
GDP	-0.4013	[0.8991]	-3.9891***	[0.0037]	-2.6043***	[0.0013]	-5.4508**	[0.0122]
OP	-5.8930	[0.0000]			-2.3246	[0.2234]		
TR	-1.8772	[0.3392]	-4.7242***	[0.0005]	-2.0428	[0.4686]	-6.3479***	[0.0008]
EXR	-2.5793	[0.1060]	-3.5489**	[0.0118]	-3.3035	[0.1142]	-7.0103***	[0.0000]

Note: ***** represent significance at the 10%, 5% and 1% levels, respectively.

Optimal Lag Length

Table 4 presents the optimal lag length results. The Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) and the Schwartz Information Criterion (SIC) were used for this study. The results reveal an optimal lag length structure of (1) for the endogenized model: FDI, OP, GDP, TR, and EXR. This implies that the effect of the outcome of the previous year on the current year is explained. We however estimated the parameters using the optimal lag length of (1).

Table 4. Optimal Lag Length Results

Lag	LogL	LR	FPE	AIC	SIC	HQ
0	-41.75623	NA	8.62e-06	2.527364	2.745055	2.604110
1	135.8568	297.6219*	2.28e-09*	-5.721991*	-4.415842*	-5.261512*
2	157.3229	30.16857	2.99e-09	-5.530970	-3.136362	-4.686758
3	192.7191	40.17937	2.11e-09	-6.092922	-2.609856	-4.864978

ARDL cointegration test

Tables 5 and 6 present results of the bounds test. The number of regressors in the model are four, hence $K = 4$. The calculated Wald F-statistic = 5.668905 and is greater than the lower bound critical value of 2.56 and the upper bound critical value of 3.49 at the 5% level of significance. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis of no long-run relationship. Therefore, the conclusion is that there is cointegration or a long-run relationship between the variables in the import demand model. The bounds testing approach has provided evidence of a long-run relationship between the variables in the model. Now the paper proceeds to estimate the long run cointegrating equation and the coefficients of the model specified.

Table 5: Bound's test

Equation	Wald F-Statistic	Lower Bound I0	Upper Bound I1	Outcome
FDI	5.668905	2.56	3.49	Cointegrated

Source: Author's calculations

Table 6. Critical value bounds

Significance	Lower Bound I0	Upper Bound I1
10%	2.2	3.09
5%	2.56	3.49
1%	3.29	4.37

Long-run Foreign Direct Investment equation

$$Cointeq = FDI_t - (-1.5190 * GDP_t + 3.2724 * OP_t + 4.8160 * EXR_t - 1.67353 * TR_t + 5.0547$$

The Long-run Unemployment equation summarizes the results of the long-term ARDL model for the model.

Table 7 presents the results of the long-term ARDL. Gross domestic product and trade were found to have a negative but not significant impact on FDI in Saudi Arabia. Exchange rate and oil price were found to have a positive and significant impact on FDI at the 10% level of significance.

Table 7. ARDL long-run FDI model

Variables	Coefficient	t-Statistic	Probability Value
GDP	-1.519027	-0.322443	0.7495
OP	3.272359	0.795690**	0.0294
TR	-1.673535	-2.29615	0.4329
EXR	4.815960	2.399874*	0.0725
C	5.054753	0.947624	0.3514

Note: **** represent significance at the 10%, 5% and 1% levels, respectively

ARDL Foreign Direct Investment ECM

Table 8 presents the results of the Short term ARDL. The individual variables were found to have the same signs they had in the long term, but different values.

Table 8. ARDL Foreign Direct Investment Error Correction Model (ECM)

Variable	Coefficient	t-Statistic	Probability Value
ΔFDI_{t-1}	-0.406911	-2.957112	0.0062
ΔGDP_{t-1}	0.618108	-0.329119	0.7445
ΔOP_{t-1}	1.331558	2.72079*	0.0814
ΔTR_{t-1}	-0.739959	-0.183528	0.8557
ΔEXR_{t-1}	1.959665	2.86457***	0.00302
ECT_{t-1}	-0.406911	-4.344303***	0.0002

Note: *** significance at the 1% level.

Discussion of the Findings

The results of the Long-term ARDL model indicate that oil prices and the real effective exchange rates do have a positive long term effect on FDI in Saudi Arabia. This contradicts the results obtained by Dal Bianco and Nguyen (2017), who found a negative relationship between exchange rates and FDI, but no relationship between oil prices and FDI. This can be explained by the country's dependency on oil, which is still a major contributor to its economic growth; thus, fluctuations in global oil prices will have an effect on the investment flow, and the rise in oil prices that occurred over the period of the study explains the positive relationship.

Additionally, we found that there was no statistically significant long-term relationship between economic growth and FDI, and also between trade openness and FDI. This is in line with Temiz and Gokemen (2014), who found no significant relationship between economic growth and FDI when they looked at Turkey, but not with Omri and Kahouli (2014), who looked at the relationship between FDI and economic growth in 13 MENA countries, and found that there was a bi-directional causality between economic growth and FDI for each of those countries, Saudi Arabia included. Our bounds test showed that FDI and economic growth were co-integrated, but the ECM model revealed that there was no directional causality between FDI and economic growth.

5 Conclusion and Recommendations

Conclusion

For our study, we used the annual WDI data for the period 1970-2019 (WDI, 2020) to assess the relationship between FDI and economic growth. While doing so, we also looked at the effect that trade openness, real exchange rates, and oil prices had had on economic growth and FDI. We used the ARDL model and the ECM as the key models to investigate this relationship. Our findings showed that real exchange rates and oil prices had been in a long-term relationship with FDI, while there had been no statistically significant long-term relationship between economic growth and trade openness. This shows that Saudi Arabia's real exchange rates and global oil price fluctuations over the years of study had been positively related with attracting FDI into the country. From the ECM test, we determined that FDI had not been Granger causally related to economic growth, which then implies that FDI had not been determined by the economic growth of Saudi Arabia. The study therefore concludes that oil price fluctuations and real exchange rates are significant factors that determine the inflow of FDI into Saudi Arabia, while economic growth and trade openness are factors that are not statistically significant in affecting such inflow.

Recommendations

This study recommends that other factors that were not included in our study due to insufficient data availability—such as research and development, corruption, political stability, and taxes—be included in future research in this area. Another recommendation is that future studies could widen their scope of research to cover more MENA countries in order to obtain comparable metrics across countries.

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